

LC-MS data processing using *xcms*

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Abstract

Liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry (LC-MS) is a key technology in metabolomics, enabling high-throughput detection of small molecules across diverse biological samples. However, raw LC-MS data is complex, requiring careful preprocessing to ensure accurate and reproducible feature detection. This chapter introduces a step-by-step protocol for LC-MS data preprocessing using the open-source *xcms* package in R. Designed for users ranging from beginners to experienced analysts, the chapter outlines critical stages including data inspection, peak detection, retention time alignment, correspondence, and result export. Special attention is given to parameter optimization and diagnostic visualization to guide users in making informed decisions tailored to their specific data set. We demonstrate the approach on human serum samples, using real-life example compounds such as proline to showcase retention time alignment and peak correspondence. By combining practical code snippets with conceptual insights, this chapter empowers researchers to harness *xcms* for robust, reproducible LC-MS workflows in untargeted metabolomics. Whether you are setting up your first analysis or refining an established pipeline, this chapter serves as both a tutorial and a reference for high-quality LC-MS data processing.

Key words

xcms, Liquid chromatography, Mass spectrometry, Metabolomics, Data processing, Preprocessing, Peak detection, Retention time correction, Quality control

1. Introduction

Liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry (LC-MS) has become a cornerstone technique in metabolomics, proteomics and other omics disciplines, such as lipidomics or DNA adductomics, due to its high sensitivity, selectivity, and ability to detect a broad range of compounds in complex biological samples. However, the raw data generated by LC-MS instruments is complex and multidimensional, requiring careful preprocessing to extract meaningful and reproducible quantitative information. Key steps of the preprocessing typically include chromatographic peak detection, retention time alignment, correspondence analysis, and gap filling. Preprocessing of LC-MS data is highly influenced by the specific LC setup and MS system used. LC-dependent influences include the type and length of the chromatography column, particle size, flow rate, gradient composition, and the chemical nature of the mobile phase (solvents, pH, buffer salts) **(1)**. These parameters affect chromatographic resolution, retention time stability (i.e., batch effects), peak shape, and the degree of co-elution between analytes **(2)**. Additionally, matrix effects arising from the sample type, such as serum, can influence retention and suppression or enhancement of signals **(3)**. MS-dependent influences relate to the instrument type (e.g., TOF, Orbitrap), ion source settings, acquisition mode (centroid vs. profile, DDA vs. DIA), mass accuracy, and resolution. These factors affect the sensitivity, dynamic range, and

spectral complexity of the acquired data, and have a direct impact on the mass deviation tolerance **(4)**. Therefore, parameters for each of the preprocessing analysis steps need to be adjusted based on the experimental setup as well as instrument configurations. A visual as well as quantitative evaluation of the data before - and during the analysis is crucial to ensure high quality results.

This chapter introduces the *xcms* R package **(5)**, a widely adopted, open-source tool designed for LC-MS data preprocessing and analysis. Developed with a strong foundation in statistical computing and reproducible research principles, *xcms* provides robust and flexible algorithms for key tasks such as peak detection, retention time correction and feature alignment across samples. Its seamless integration with the broader R ecosystem allows for the entire workflow, from initial inspection to normalization and downstream statistical analysis, to be executed within a single, reproducible environment. Moreover, *xcms* is optimized to handle computationally intensive, big data sets, making it suitable for both exploratory and large-scale studies.

In detail, we will demonstrate a complete, reproducible LC-MS data preprocessing workflow using *xcms*, illustrated with a small untargeted LC-MS metabolomics data set. Special emphasis is placed on the best practices for data handling, parameter optimization, and quality control. By the end of this chapter, readers will have a strong foundation in using *xcms* to transform raw LC-MS data into structured high-quality feature tables suitable for downstream statistical analysis and biological interpretation.

2. Material

This provides an overview of the data set, software environment, and workflow used for LC-MS(/MS) data preprocessing with the *xcms* R package. The entire analysis is designed to be reproducible and made publicly available.

2.1 Overview of the workflow

To make the data processing steps transparent and reproducible, the analysis performed in this chapter is also implemented as a Quarto document (.qmd). [Quarto](#) enables seamless integration of code, narrative, and output, allowing readers to execute and modify the workflow directly (see **Note 1**). While any code editor may be used, [RStudio](#) offers built-in support for both R and Quarto and is a commonly used interface in data science.

As LC-MS preprocessing is strongly influenced by the specific setup used, there is no single set of parameters that fits all configurations, hence, settings for each preprocessing algorithm need to be defined and evaluated on the actual experimental data. This workflow shows examples to derive data set-specific settings for each preprocessing step and tools to evaluate their impact. Depending on the data it might be needed to test and evaluate different settings to adapt them to the experiment.

2.2 Data set

The LC-MS data used in this chapter comes from a small, publicly available untargeted metabolomics study. It can be found on the [MassIVE](#) repository (accession: MSV000099121) and can be downloaded from the archive for use in this tutorial.

Samples were analyzed using HILIC UPLC-QTOF-MS in positive ionization modes, as described in (6). Raw data files are provided in the open and vendor-independent .mzML format (see **Note 2**).

The data set consists of pooled human serum samples, which represent internal quality control (QC) samples, each spiked with a set of 15 compounds at two concentration levels: high and low. Each sample was measured in the positive ionisation mode and as a technical triplicate to assess reproducibility (Table 1).

Table 1. Experimental design of the small untargeted metabolomics data set.

mzML	polarity	time	mode	collision_energy	concentration	sample_name	sample_origin	sample_type
QC_LowIS_Mix13_1_POS.mzML	POS	2020-01-17 14:33:51	MS1		low	low_a	serum	pool QC
QC_HighIS_Mix13_3_POS.mzML	POS	2020-01-17 14:51:21	MS1		high	high_c	serum	pool QC
QC_LowIS_Mix13_3_POS.mzML	POS	2020-01-17 15:46:56	MS1		low	low_c	serum	pool QC
QC_HighIS_Mix13_2_POS.mzML	POS	2020-01-17 17:58:34	MS1		high	high_b	serum	pool QC
QC_LowIS_Mix13_2_POS.mzML	POS	2020-01-17 20:48:23	MS1		low	low_b	serum	pool QC
QC_HighIS_Mix13_1_POS.mzML	POS	2020-01-17 22:48:18	MS1		high	high_a	serum	pool QC
QC_HighIS_Mix13_CE20_PO S.mzML	POS	2020-01-18 19:27:09	DDA	20	high	high_20	serum	pool QC
QC_HighIS_Mix13_CE30_PO S.mzML	POS	2020-01-18 19:39:02	DDA	30	high	high_30	serum	pool QC

Additionally, two LC-MS/MS runs were acquired for one of the high concentration samples using data-dependent acquisition (DDA) at two different collision energies (20 eV and 30 eV). These are included to support downstream MS/MS-based compound annotation (Table 1).

2.3 Software and R packages

The data analysis was performed using R (version 4.5.0), a statistical programming language available for Windows and Unix (Linux, and macOS) systems.

The core LC-MS(/MS) preprocessing workflow is built upon the following R packages:

1. *Spectra* is used to import and handle the raw mass spectrometry data, providing efficient and flexible access to spectral information **(7)**.
2. *MsExperiment* is employed to manage the experimental design and to link sample metadata with the corresponding raw data files **(8)**.
3. *xcms* performs key preprocessing steps including chromatographic peak detection, retention time alignment, and correspondence analysis **(5)**.

Complementary packages that enhance and support mainly metabolomics-specific analyses include:

1. *MetaboCoreUtils* offers core utility functions for metabolomics data processing, including mass-to-charge (m/z) and retention time calculations, adduct annotation, and common data transformations used across multiple packages **(9)**.
2. *SummarizedExperiment* provides Bioconductor's standardized container for storing assay data (e.g., feature intensities) alongside row (feature) and column (sample)

metadata, facilitating consistent data handling and integration in metabolomics workflows **(10)**.

3. *MsBackendMgf* implements support for reading and writing mass spectral data in the Mascot Generic Format (MGF), commonly used for storing MS/MS spectra in metabolomics and proteomics annotation tasks **(11)**.

All these packages are part of Bioconductor **(12)(13)** and can be installed using the *BiocManager* R package (see **Note 3**).

Additional R packages support the workflow by enabling data visualization (*RColorBrewer*, *pheatmap*), reading of metadata and tabular input files (*data.table*), and providing utility functions that enhance reproducibility and automation (*knitr*, *BiocStyle*).

2.4 Reproducible analysis workflow

To ensure complete reproducibility **(14)** of the present analysis, the workflow as well as the data are publicly available through GitHub and MassIVE respectively. Users can either manually install all required dependencies, or load and run a Docker image that contains the workflow, the data and all required software allowing interactive evaluation of the code locally on the user's computer.

Information on the workflow files, data and installation instructions are available at <https://github.com/jorainer/xcms-preprocessing-protocol>.

3. Methods

Before the actual data processing, the experimental setup should be defined and the data files/samples organized. The experimental setup is best defined using a spreadsheet with one data files per row and columns containing the technical and phenotypical properties of each data file respectively the sample (such as shown in **Table 1**). Ideally, samples/files should be added in the order in which they were measured. For the present analysis it is assumed that all MS data files are placed into a folder *data/mzML*, and the spreadsheet with sample annotation to the folder *data*.

3.1 Data import

In this section, general setup steps are performed, including loading the required R packages, configuring parallel processing, and specifying the data directory. The sample metadata and raw LC-MS data are then loaded and color-coded to facilitate clear and consistent visualization throughout the analysis.

1. Load all required R/Bioconductor packages for the present analysis (see **Note 3**).

```
#' Load all R packages
library(xcms)
library(MsExperiment)
library(Spectra)
library(RColorBrewer)
library(pheatmap)
library(MetaboCoreUtils)
library(SummarizedExperiment)
library(MsBackendMgf)
```

2. Configure parallel processing. Configure the number of cores, using the `CORES` variable. All data analysis functions in `xcms` have built-in parallel processing capabilities. In addition, to reduce memory load, `xcms` performs analyses in a *chunk-wise manner*, i.e., only data from a certain number of samples is loaded and processed at a time. This can be configured with the parameter `chunkSize =` in most data analysis functions. Importantly, the number of CPU cores used should be smaller or equal to the value for this parameter. Below we chose to use 2 CPU cores for parallel processing. R supports on Unix systems the *multi-core* parallel processing, while on Windows systems *simple network of workstation (SNOW)*-based parallel processing must be used.

```
#' Define the number of cores
CORES <- 2

#' Set up parallel processing using 2 cores
if (.Platform$OS.type == "unix") {
  register(MulticoreParam(CORES))
} else {
  register(SnowParam(CORES))
}
```

3. Load experimental setup/sample information. It is good practice to define the experimental setup using e.g., a spreadsheet that contains the names of all of the experiment's data files (eventually including their path) and their respective samples including all phenotypical information as well as technical/experimental properties. Ideally, the order of the samples should match their injection sequence. The content of the spreadsheet for the present experiment is shown in Table 1. Load the

experiment's spreadsheet using the `read.csv()` function from the *data.table* R package (see **Note 4**).

```
#' Import sample file
sample_data <- read.csv("data/standards_mzml.csv")
```

4. Create a *data representation* for the experiment. The `readMsExperiment()` function takes the names of the data files (including the path to the directory where they are stored, configured below using the `MZML_PATH` variable) and a `data.frame` with the sample information for the respective data files as input. The resulting `MsExperiment` object (variable `ms_data`) contains a reference to the MS data files and the sample information.

```
#' Define the path to the directory where the data files can be found
MZML_PATH <- file.path("data/mzML/")
```

```
#' Linking the raw data to its respective metadata.
ms_data <- readMsExperiment(file.path(MZML_PATH, sample_data$mzML),
                           sampleData = sample_data)
```

5. Check if the *data representation* is correct by printing the sample information table (Table 2). Sample information can be extracted using the `sampleData()` function.

```
#' View the sample information table
sampleData(ms_data)[, c("mzML", "sample_name", "mode",
                        "collision_energy",
                        "concentration")] |>
  kable(format = "pipe")
```

Table 2. Data files and samples.

mzML	sample_name	mode	collision_energy	concentration
QC_LowIS_Mix13_1_POS.mzML	low_a	MS1	NA	low
QC_HighIS_Mix13_3_POS.mzML	high_c	MS1	NA	high
QC_LowIS_Mix13_3_POS.mzML	low_c	MS1	NA	low

QC_HighIS_Mix13_2_POS.mzML	high_b	MS1	NA	high
QC_LowIS_Mix13_2_POS.mzML	low_b	MS1	NA	low
QC_HighIS_Mix13_1_POS.mzML	high_a	MS1	NA	high
QC_HighIS_Mix13_CE20_POS.mzML	high_20	DDA	20	high
QC_HighIS_Mix13_CE30_POS.mzML	high_30	DDA	30	high

6. Define colors to label individual or groups of samples (see **Note 5**).

```
# ' Define colors by concentration levels: high and low
col_concentration <- c(low = "#FF7F00", high = "#A65628")
col_sample <- col_concentration[sampleData(ms_data)$concentration]
```

3.2 Initial data inspection

Before initiating the preprocessing of LC-MS data, it is essential to evaluate the overall data quality and define key parameters. In this section, we perform the visual inspection of the base peak chromatogram (BPC) and extracted-ion chromatograms (EICs), enabling the identification of poorly acquired samples, retention time regions with meaningful signal, and potential contaminants. We also verify whether the data was acquired in centroid mode, a requirement for peak detection, and extract signal characteristics such as chromatographic peak width and m/z mass deviation using the example compounds. An EIC visualizes the measured signal (intensity) for a particular ion of a compound along the retention time axis. It allows inspection of the number of available data points and the shape of the elution pattern. While for the present example we extract the EIC only for proline, a metabolite that is known to be present in human serum samples, for real experiments signal for multiple compounds or ions, ideally from retention time regions along the full retention time range, should be extracted and their signal evaluated. These initial steps help ensure that the data

is suitable for automated processing and allow optimization of parameter settings for robust peak detection and alignment.

3.2.1 Visualize base peak chromatogram

1. Create a base peak chromatogram of the full data set and plot it (Figure 1). The BPC is plotted to assess chromatographic drift or shifts, sample quality or outliers, and the presence of systematic noise or chemical contamination (e.g., polymer peaks). With parameter `aggregationFun = "max"` the highest intensity per spectrum is reported, while setting `aggregationFun = "sum"` would sum-up all intensities per spectrum, hence generating a total ion chromatogram (TIC).

```
#' Create a BPC
bpc <- chromatogram(ms_data, aggregationFun = "max", chunkSize =
CORES)

#' Plot the BPC
plot(bpc, col = paste0(col_sample, 80), main = "")
grid()
abline(v = c(15, 225), lty = 2)
legend("topright", col = col_concentration, lty = 1,
      legend = names(col_concentration))
```

3.2.2 Retention time filtering

2. To focus analysis on the region where meaningful compound separation and detection occur, filter the data to a specific retention time window, e.g., for the present data set, between 15 and 225 seconds. This can be guided by known elution times of spiked or expected endogenous compounds.

```
#' Filter retention time
ms_data <- filterSpectra(ms_data, filterRt, c(15, 225))
```

3. Create a BPC of the retention time-filtered data set for further evaluation under **Section 3.3.2**.

```
#' Extract the BPC again - for reference later.
bpc <- chromatogram(ms_data, aggregationFun = "max", chunkSize =
CORES)
```

3.2.3 Extracted-ion chromatogram selection

4. Determine the m/z range for proline. Starting from its chemical formula $C_5H_9NO_2$, calculate the theoretical isotopic mass and subsequently the theoretical m/z for one of its ions. We use "[M+H]+" as the most likely adduct of proline in positive polarity, but could also specify any other possible adduct, such as "[M+Na]+", "[M+NH₄]+" etc. Create a range around the theoretical m/z by subtracting and adding a value of 0.01 Da. Depending on the accuracy and precision of the MS instrument, this value might be increased or decreased.

```
#' Calculate the mass of proline
proline_formula <- "C5H9NO2"
proline_mass <- calculateMass(proline_formula)

#' Calculate m/z for an adduct of proline
proline_mz <- mass2mz(proline_mass, c("[M+H]+"))[1, ]
proline_mzr <- cbind(mzmin = proline_mz - 0.01, mzmax = proline_mz +
0.01)
```

5. Extract and plot the EIC of proline (Figure 2).

```
#' Extract the EIC for proline
proline_eic <- chromatogram(ms_data, mz = proline_mzr,
                           rt = c(160, 200), chunkSize = CORES)

#' Plot the EIC for proline
```

```
plot(proline_eic, col = paste0(col_sample, 80), xlim = c(165, 175))
grid()
```

6. Repeat this for minimum 10 compounds and save the EIC objects. Inspect molecules that you have spiked (e.g., internal standards), are known to be endogenously present (e.g., amino acids in serum), or select unknown compounds (see **Note 6**). Be aware to select compounds with retention time and m/z values representing the full chromatogram and mass spectrum range, respectively. If the expected retention time range is unknown, omit the parameter `rt` of the `chromatogram()` function and extract the ion trace for the full full retention time range (Figure 3).

```
## Extract the EIC for an unknown compound
unknown_eic <- chromatogram(ms_data, mz = c(106.0399, 106.0599),
                           chunkSize = CORES)

## Plot the full EIC
plot(unknown_eic, col = paste0(col_sample, 80))
grid()
```

3.2.4 Check m/z data acquisition mode

7. Evaluate whether data is acquired in centroid (see **Note 7**) mode in the first sample, using proline (Figure 4). In addition, determine the variance in peaks' m/z along the retention time axis for individual ions. For better readability of the code, the R *pipe operator* (`|>`) is used to concatenate subsequent function calls.

```
## Check if data is in centroid mode
ms_data_proline <- ms_data[1] |>
  filterSpectra(filterRt, c(167, 172)) |>
  filterSpectra(filterMzRange, proline_mzr[1, ])
```

```
plot(ms_data_proline)
```

3.3 Data preprocessing

In this section, we outline the essential steps of LC-MS data preprocessing using the *xcms* package. Chromatographic peak detection identifies relevant features in the raw MS data based on intensity patterns across retention time and mass-to-charge ratio. Retention time shifts between measurement runs are then adjusted in the retention time alignment step. The subsequent correspondence analysis groups chromatographic peaks from different samples that represent the same adduct or isotopic form of the same underlying compound defining thus the *LC-MS features*. This grouping across samples relies on similarity of the chromatographic peak's *m/z* and retention time values and depends thus on a successful reduction of retention time shifts between the samples. Finally, gap filling recovers missing intensity values where peaks were not initially detected, producing a complete and consistent feature table ready for downstream statistical analysis.

The *xcms* package provides several different algorithms for each of these steps. In the present example we use the most robust and commonly used methods. Also, importantly, settings for these algorithms need to be adapted to the analyzed data set. These are best defined using visual inspection of the data and evaluation of the results, eventually requiring changing and optimizing the parameters in several iterations.

3.3.1 Chromatographic peak detection

We will use the *centWave* algorithm (**15**) for chromatographic peak detection. The most important parameters for this algorithm are peakwidth, which defines the expected range of chromatographic peak widths (in retention time dimension) in the data set, and ppm that defines the maximal acceptable deviation (in m/z dimension) of mass peaks for a certain ion in consecutive spectra. Other parameters for which different values than the default are used are snthresh (signal-to-noise threshold) and integrate. snthresh defines the trade-off between the number of false positive and negative peaks. Parameter integrate allows to select the method to define the chromatographic peaks boundaries in retention time dimension. The default integrate = 1 assumes symmetric, gaussian-shaped peaks, while integrate = 2 uses a method that defines peak boundaries through local minimas in peak intensities.

1. Define the peakwidth parameter. Inspect extracted chromatographic peaks of the ≥ 10 plotted EICs and determine the average observed width of the peaks in retention time dimension. The rule of thumb is: choose an initial peakwidth to be between half of the observed peak width to maximum the double peak width (in seconds). Values 2 and 10 for the lower and upper expected peak width seem to be appropriate for the present data set. Evaluate the impact and result of this choice by applying the chromatographic peak detection on the EICs extracted in **Section 3.2**. The parameters for the *centWave* algorithm are configured with the CentWaveParam() function and peak detection is performed using findChromPeaks(). Note that a very

low value for `snthresh` is used for peak detection in EIC signals because of the lack of background signal to properly estimate noise. Repeat this analysis for all EICs. Values for the `peakwidth` parameter should be adjusted if the results don't match the expectations.

```
#' Define the peak detection settings
cwp <- CentWaveParam(peakwidth = c(2, 10),
                    snthresh = 1,
                    integrate = 2)

#' Perform peak detection for the proline EIC
proline_eic <- findChromPeaks(proline_eic, param = cwp)
```

2. Plot and visually inspect the chromatographic peak detection results of the EIC (Figure 5).

```
#' Plot the proline EIC after peak detections
plot(proline_eic,
     peakCol = paste0(col_sample[chromPeaks(proline_eic)[, "column"]],
                      80),
     peakBg = paste0(col_sample[chromPeaks(proline_eic)[, "column"]],
                     40),
     col = col_sample, xlim = c(165, 175))
```

3. Calculate the average peak width in retention time dimension. This value across all EICs can be used to evaluate whether peak width match the expectation from the LC setup.

```
#' Calculate the mean rt peak width
(chromPeaks(proline_eic)[, "rtmax"] -
 chromPeaks(proline_eic)[, "rtmin"]) |>
  mean()
```

```
[1] 5.744353
```

4. Define the *centWave* ppm parameter. Using the tentative MS signal for proline from **Section 3.2.4** (i.e., the MS data from its approximate *m/z* and retention time window) the parts-per-million (ppm, see **Note 8**) deviation of the mass peaks' *m/z* values is calculated. This should be repeated for each of the ≥ 10 plotted EICs. Use the calculated values to define parameter ppm. Note that it is absolutely acceptable to use larger values for ppm than observed, in particular for data from time-of-flight (TOF) instruments where *m/z* deviation generally increases with lower intensities. Thus, to ensure that chromatographic peak boundaries are correctly estimated, it can be beneficial to use higher than observed values for the parameter ppm. For the present data set we use ppm = 5.

```
#' Estimate m/z deviation for proline
mz_diff <- spectra(ms_data_proline) |>
  mz() |>
  unlist() |>
  diff()

ppm <- max(mz_diff) / proline_mz * 10^6
print(paste0("The expected ppm for proline is: ", round(ppm, 3)))

[1] "The expected ppm for proline is: 1.279"
```

5. Perform chromatographic peak detection with the defined settings on the whole data set. Set parameter *sntresh* depending on whether only high abundance, high quality peaks should be detected (i.e., use a value ≥ 10), or also low abundance peaks, accepting eventually false positive peaks. For *sntresh*, we use a value of 5 (instead of the default 10).

```

#' Define the peak detection settings
cwp <- CentWaveParam(peakwidth = c(2, 10),
                    ppm = 5,
                    snthresh = 5,
                    integrate = 2)

#' Perform peak detection on the full data
ms_data <- findChromPeaks(ms_data, param = cwp, chunkSize = CORES)

```

6. Perform peak refinement (optional, but suggested for *centWave*). This step can help correct peak detection artifacts of the *centWave* algorithm. It should however be used with caution, as it may also introduce artificial corrections if not properly evaluated. By merging neighboring peaks, closely eluting or overlapping peaks that likely originate from the same compound are combined. This helps reduce redundancy and improves the accuracy of downstream analyses. Parameter `expandRt` should be set to a value close to, or smaller than, half of the average observed retention time width of chromatographic peaks and for `ppm` the same value as used for *centWave* peak detection can be used.

```

#' Define the peak refinement settings
mnpp <- MergeNeighboringPeaksParam(expandRt = 3,
                                   ppm = 5)

#' Perform peak refinement
ms_data <- refineChromPeaks(ms_data, param = mnpp, chunkSize = CORES)

```

Reduced from 70363 to 63236 chromatographic peaks.

7. Summaries of identified peaks: determine the number of identified peaks per sample (Table 3). Especially pay attention to the number of peaks per sample, and to the quantiles of retention time widths and *m/z* widths.

```
#' View summary of identified peaks
data.frame(sample_name = sampleData(ms_data)$sample_name,
            peak_count = as.integer(table(chromPeaks(ms_data)[,
"sample"]))) |>
  t() |>
  kable(format = "pipe")
```

```
sample_na  low  high  low  high  low  high  high_  high_
me          _a  _c   _c   _b   _b   _a    20    30

peak_coun  927  1195  905  1184  902  1172    188    172
t          0    0    6    7    9    4
```

Table 3. Summary of peaks count per sample.

sample_name	Peak_count
low_a	927
high_c	1195
low_c	905
high_b	1184
low_b	902
high_a	1172
high_20	188
high_30	172

8. Summaries of identified peaks: evaluate the m/z widths of identified chromatographic peaks. Calculate the distribution (quantiles) of the chromatographic peak widths in m/z dimension.

```
#' Distribution of m/z peak widths
(chromPeaks(ms_data)[, "mzmax"] -
 chromPeaks(ms_data)[, "mzmin"]) |>
  quantile()

          0%          25%          50%          75%          100%
0.000000000 0.001056088 0.001863562 0.003020259 0.034988519
```

9. Summaries of identified peaks: evaluate the retention time widths of identified chromatographic peaks. Calculate the distribution (quantiles) of the chromatographic peak widths in retention time dimension.

```
#' Distribution of retention time peak widths
(chromPeaks(ms_data)[, "rtmax"] -
 chromPeaks(ms_data)[, "rtmin"]) |>
  quantile()

0%      25%      50%      75%     100%
0.641  1.674  2.232  3.627  83.423
```

3.3.2 Retention time alignment

Retention time alignment aims at adjusting the data for retention times shifts between measurement runs (i.e., samples) **(16)**. We use the *peak groups* method from *xcms*. This algorithm performs a robust, non-linear alignment based on retention times of signals, the so called *anchor peaks*, that are present in most samples. This requires an initial, loose, grouping of chromatographic peaks across samples. This grouping of chromatographic peaks to features does not need to be perfect yet, i.e., the signal from different ions may be grouped into the same feature, as retention time alignment will correct for systematic shifts. Grouping collects peaks that represent the same compound across samples, even if retention times differ slightly. The *peak groups* alignment method can then select anchor peaks among these initial LC-MS features and align the samples by minimizing the retention time differences between the anchor peaks.

1. Perform an initial correspondence analysis using the *peak density* method. Define the sample groups of the experiment and exclude samples that should not be

considered for peak grouping/alignment by assigning NA. In the present example LC-MS/MS measurements are excluded. Set parameters minFraction depending on the experimental setting. We use minFraction = 2/3, thus, to define a feature, a chromatographic peak has to be present in at least two out of the 3 samples per sample group. Parameters binSize and ppm depend on the resolution of the MS instrumentation and proper calibration across measurement runs. Chromatographic peaks (within and between samples) with a difference in m/z value smaller than binSize + ppm of the peaks' m/z will be grouped into a feature. Choices should depend on the maximal expected absolute difference of m/z values for signals of the same compound in different sample runs. Parameter ppm allows to account for the m/z -dependent measurement error frequently observed on TOF-based instruments. The value for parameter bw depends on the observed difference of retention times between isomers as well as retention time shifts between samples. For this initial correspondence analysis it should be set to a larger value to allow/account for retention time differences between samples. A value close to or larger than the average observed retention time width of detected chromatographic peaks could be a good initial choice.

```
#' Define sample groups and set samples that should not be
#' considered to `NA`
grp <- sampleData(ms_data)$concentration
grp[sampleData(ms_data)$mode == "DDA"] <- NA

#' Define the settings for the initial correspondence
pdp <- PeakDensityParam(sampleGroups = grp,
                        minFraction = 2 / 3,
                        binSize = 0.02,
```

```
ppm = 10,  
bw = 4)
```

```
#' Perform the initial correspondence analysis  
ms_data <- groupChromPeaks(ms_data, param = pdp)
```

2. Perform retention time alignment to correct systematic shifts between samples using the *peak groups* method. Configure the algorithm using `PeakGroupsParam()`.
Parameters: `minFraction`: minimum fraction of samples that must share an anchor peak for alignment. This is relative to the total number of samples, not the number of samples per sample group (as above). Choices around 0.8 (presence of an anchor peak in 80% of samples) work for most experiments. We use a value of 0.9 as the same sample was repeatedly measured. `extraPeaks`: number of extra peaks per feature considered for robust alignment (optimally use a value similar to the number of samples in the experiment). `span`: controls the smoothness of the alignment curve. Must be a value between 0 and 1, smaller values fit more local variation, a value of 1 would perform a constant shift. A value between 0.4 and 0.7 works in most cases. Parameter `subset` allows to configure an alignment that is based only on a subset of samples (such as e.g., quality control (QC) samples). Set `subset` to the indices of such QC samples or to the indices of the samples on which the initial correspondence was performed.

```
#' Define retention time alignment parameters  
pgp <- PeakGroupsParam(minFraction = 0.9,  
                       extraPeaks = length(ms_data),  
                       span = 0.4,  
                       subset = which(!is.na(grp)))
```

```
#' Perform retention time alignment
ms_data <- adjustRtime(ms_data, param = pgp, chunkSize = CORES)
```

Performing retention time correction using 3395 peak groups.

Aligning sample number 7 against subset ... OK

Aligning sample number 8 against subset ... OK

3. Evaluate alignment result. Plot the adjusted retention times (x-axis) against the difference between raw and adjusted retention times (y-axis) for each sample as a line (Figure 6). Deviations observed on the y-axis should meet the expectations from the variance generally observed on the employed LC setup. Data points (i.e., anchor peaks) should span most of the retention time range. If needed, adapt parameters and repeat the initial correspondence and alignment.

```
#' Plot the adjusted rt vs. rt differences before and after correction
plotAdjustedRtime(ms_data, col = paste0(col_sample, 80))
grid()
```

4. Create the BPC after retention time alignment to visually compare with the original BPC (Figure 7).

```
#' Create the BPC after rt alignment
bpc_adj <- chromatogram(ms_data, chromPeaks = "none", aggregationFun =
"max",
                        chunkSize = CORES)
```

```
#' Plot before and after rt alignment
par(mfrow = c(2, 1))
plot(bpc, col = paste0(col_sample, 60), main = "raw data")
grid()
plot(bpc_adj, col = paste0(col_sample, 60),
     main = "aligned data")
grid()
```

5. Evaluate improved retention time alignment on each EICs (Figure 8).

```
#' Extract the EIC for proline with corrected rt
proline_eic_adj <- chromatogram(ms_data, mz = proline_mzr,
                               chunkSize = CORES)

Processing chromatographic peaks

#' Plot before and after rt alignment for proline EIC
par(mfrow = c(2, 1))
plot(proline_eic[1, ], col = paste0(col_sample, 80),
     peakType = "none", xlim = c(165, 175))
grid()
plot(proline_eic_adj[1, ], col = paste0(col_sample, 80),
     peakType = "none", xlim = c(165, 175))
grid()
```

6. Apply the alignment results to the data set.

```
#' Apply the corrected rt to data set
ms_data <- applyAdjustedRtime(ms_data)
```

3.3.3 Correspondence analysis

Correspondence analysis groups signals (chromatographic peaks) across samples that are presumably from the same original ion. This grouping depends on similarity of the peaks' m/z and retention time values.

1. Derive settings for correspondence analysis. Extract the signal trace for the m/z of EICs defined in **Section 3.2.3**. Define parameters for the correspondence: values for `binSize` and `ppm` can be adopted from the initial correspondence analysis from **Section 3.3.2**. Parameter `minFraction` should be adapted to match the experimental

setup. For `bw`, use the same value, or a smaller value, than used for the initial correspondence. Generally, smaller values are used to perform a more strict grouping. Plot the resulting EIC and simulate a correspondence analysis with the defined configuration (Figure 9).

```
#' Extract EIC for the full rt range for EICs' m/z ranges
eic <- chromatogram(ms_data, mz = proline_mzr, chunkSize = CORES)

Processing chromatographic peaks

#' Configure correspondence analysis
pdp <- PeakDensityParam(sampleGroups = grp,
                        minFraction = 2 / 3,
                        binSize = 0.02,
                        ppm = 10,
                        bw = 2)

#' Plot EIC and simulate correspondence
plotChromPeakDensity(eic, param = pdp, col = paste0(col_sample, 80))
grid()
```

2. Evaluate the resulting plot. Are chromatographic peaks grouped properly into features? Chromatographic peaks, respectively the retention time of their apex, grouped into the same feature are indicated with grey rectangles in the lower part of the plot. Are co- or closely eluting compounds separated into distinct features? Evaluate the results on all EICs defined in **Section 3.2.3**. Eventually change one or more parameters of `PeakDensityParam()` and repeat until results are satisfactory. Eventually reduce the value for `bw` to avoid grouping of closely eluting, but distinct, compounds into the same features.
3. Perform the correspondence analysis on the full data set (Figure 10).

```

#' Final correspondence
ms_data <- groupChromPeaks(ms_data, param = pdp)

Evaluate results on EICs. Extract ion traces for the m/z ranges of
EICs from Section 3.2.3 and plot the correspondence results using
plotChromPeakDensity(). Use parameter simulate = FALSE to show the
actual correspondence results. Repeat for all m/z ranges from Section
3.2.3.

#' Extract EIC for the full rt range for EICs' m/z ranges
eic <- chromatogram(ms_data, mz = proline_mzr, chunkSize = CORES)

Processing chromatographic peaks

Processing features

#' Plot EIC and simulate correspondence
plotChromPeakDensity(eic, col = paste0(col_sample, 80),
                    simulate = FALSE)

grid()

```

5. Visualize the features's *m/z* and retention times in the full *m/z* and retention time space of the data set (Figure 11). To avoid loading the *m/z* values of all mass peaks we manually define the *m/z* range based on the MS instrument setup. Use `ylim = range(unlist(mz(spectra(ms_data))))` to calculate it from the data set.

```

#' Plot m/z vs. rt for the data set
plot(NA, NA, xlim = range(runtime(spectra(ms_data))),
     ylim = c(0, 1000),
     xlab = "retention time", ylab = "m/z")
grid()
points(featureDefinitions(ms_data)$rtmed,
       featureDefinitions(ms_data)$mzmed,
       pch = 21, col = "#00000060", bg = "#00000020")

```

3.3.4 Gap filling

The feature abundance matrix reports values for identified chromatographic peaks. This matrix can contain a considerable number of missing values depending on whether for a particular feature a chromatographic peak was detected in a sample or not. The gap filling step aims at reducing the number of missing values by integrating all raw MS signal from the feature's expected m/z and retention time window in samples in which no chromatographic peak was detected.

1. Determine the percentage of missing values in the feature abundance matrix.

```
#' Get the total number, and the number of missing values
total_feat <- length(featureValues(ms_data))
miss_feat <- sum(is.na(featureValues(ms_data)))
```

```
#' Calculate the percentage of missing values in the data set
miss_feat / total_feat * 100
```

```
[1] 51.8038
```

Perform the gap filling.

```
#' Perform gap filling
ms_data <- fillChromPeaks(ms_data, ChromPeakAreaParam(),
                          chunkSize = CORES)
```

Determine the number of missing values after gap filling.

```
#' Get the number of missing values after gap filling
miss_feat <- sum(is.na(featureValues(ms_data)))
```

```
#' Calculate the percentage of missing values in the data set
miss_feat / total_feat * 100
```

```
[1] 28.40485
```

3.4 Post processing and data export

Following the preprocessing, the resulting feature table represents the foundation for downstream statistical analysis and biological interpretation. This post-processing phase typically involves several key steps to refine and analyze the data further. These include normalization of feature intensities across samples to correct for systematic variation, removal of outlier features that may represent technical artifacts, and assessment of sample variance to identify trends or inconsistencies.

Subsequently, differential abundance analysis is performed to identify metabolic features that distinguish phenotypes or experimental conditions of interest. Multivariate statistical methods, such as principal component analysis (PCA), hierarchical clustering, (orthogonal) partial least squares discriminant analysis ((O)PLS-DA), linear regression-based approaches, or machine learning algorithms are often employed to visualize global patterns and highlight relevant features.

Finally, metabolite annotation of significant or interesting features is a critical step for biological interpretation, enabling insights into the metabolic pathways or processes involved. The exact post-processing workflow may vary depending on the research question, experimental design, and biological matrix.

For practical code examples and guidance on the post processing, we refer the reader to the many [example workflows](#) of the Metabonaut resource **(17)**, which provides detailed and modular R-based workflows for each component of post-processing.

After completing preprocessing, and optionally some further data filtering and/or normalization, the feature table can be exported for downstream analysis, sharing, or archiving. This step ensures reproducibility and allows interoperability with other software tools for statistical analysis or metabolite identification. Below, we outline key procedures to export the processed data, including both the feature intensity matrix and the features' MS/MS spectra.

1. Export feature table as a `SummarizedExperiment` object (see **Note 9**). Parameter `filled = FALSE` extracts only abundances of detected chromatographic peaks, but no gap-filled values.

```
#' Extract feature intensity results as a SummarizedExperiment
res <- quantify(ms_data, method = "sum", filled = FALSE)

#' View the summary of the result object
res

class: SummarizedExperiment
dim: 13132 8
metadata(6): '' '' ... '' ''
assays(1): raw
rownames(13132): FT00001 FT00002 ... FT13131 FT13132
rowData names(10): mzmed mzmin ... low ms_level
colnames(8): QC_LowIS_Mix13_1_POS.mzML QC_HighIS_Mix13_3_POS.mzML ...
  QC_HighIS_Mix13_CE20_POS.mzML QC_HighIS_Mix13_CE30_POS.mzML
colData names(11): mzML polarity ... X spectraOrigin
```

2. Add a second assay containing missing-value filled data to the `SummarizedExperiment` object. The additional assay contains filled intensity values (i.e., using gap-filling methods for missing peaks), so it can be used in downstream imputation-aware analysis.

```
#' Add a second assay named 'raw_filled' with gap-filled intensities
assays(res)$raw_filled <- featureValues(ms_data, method = "sum",
                                         filled = TRUE )
```

```
#' View different assays in the SummarizedExperiment object
assayNames(res)
```

```
[1] "raw"          "raw_filled"
```

```
#' View the top of the filled feature intensity matrix
assay(res, "raw_filled") |> head()
```

```
      QC_LowIS_Mix13_1_POS.mzML QC_HighIS_Mix13_3_POS.mzML
FT00001          1875.43619          790.0453
FT00002           22.48469          6331.4319
FT00003          273.61998          151.5588
FT00004          262.42877             NA
FT00005             NA          523.0190
FT00006          6192.42353          6119.8266
      QC_LowIS_Mix13_3_POS.mzML QC_HighIS_Mix13_2_POS.mzML
FT00001          1174.224766          963.4551
FT00002           5.983196          5514.1061
FT00003          191.085146          699.5291
FT00004          350.285451             NA
FT00005             NA          804.6854
FT00006          4453.887713          5858.3308
      QC_LowIS_Mix13_2_POS.mzML QC_HighIS_Mix13_1_POS.mzML
FT00001          736.556377          1624.94089
FT00002           8.051912          2952.14927
FT00003          201.881637          1031.20904
FT00004          313.886706           30.46919
FT00005             NA          260.96907
FT00006          2450.053783          3310.73301
      QC_HighIS_Mix13_CE20_POS.mzML QC_HighIS_Mix13_CE30_POS.mzML
FT00001             NA             NA
FT00002          8947.748             NA
FT00003          4533.783             NA
FT00004             NA             NA
FT00005             NA             NA
FT00006             NA             NA
```

- Export the feature abundance matrix to a spreadsheet. The ID of the features and their *m/z* and retention time are added as additional columns to this feature

abundance matrix. For ease of data sharing or as input into external tools (e.g., Excel, Python), the feature intensity matrix can be exported as a .csv file.

```
#' Compile a data.frame with feature definitions and abundances
fd_data <- data.frame(
  feature_id = rownames(rowData(res)),
  rowData(res)[, c("mzmed", "rtmed")],
  assay(res, "raw_filled")
)

#' Write the filled feature intensity matrix to a CSV file
write.csv(fd_data,
  file = "data/standards_abundance.csv")
```

4. Export the MS/MS spectra in MGF format. To support metabolite annotation in external tools (e.g., GNPS, MS-DIAL, SIRIUS, or MzMine), the MS/MS spectra associated with detected MS features are exported to the Mascot Generic Format (MGF). The `MsBackendMgf()` backend function is used here to write the compatible files. To allow association between the exported feature abundances and the MS/MS spectra, the MGF file contains a field *feature_id* containing the identifier of the feature for each MS/MS spectrum.

```
#' Extract the MS/MS spectra for each feature
sp <- featureSpectra(ms_data)

#' Export the MS/MS spectra in .mgf format
export(sp, MsBackendMgf(), file = "data/std_spectra.mgf")
```

3.5 Session information

1. Print the R session info in the rendered Quarto document (see **Note 10**).

```
#' View R session info
sessionInfo()
```

R version 4.5.0 (2025-04-11 ucrt)
Platform: x86_64-w64-mingw32/x64
Running under: Windows 11 x64 (build 22631)

Matrix products: default
LAPACK version 3.12.1

locale:

[1] LC_COLLATE=English_United States.utf8
[2] LC_CTYPE=English_United States.utf8
[3] LC_MONETARY=English_United States.utf8
[4] LC_NUMERIC=C
[5] LC_TIME=English_United States.utf8

time zone: Europe/Rome
tzcode source: internal

attached base packages:

[1] stats4 stats graphics grDevices utils datasets
methods
[8] base

other attached packages:

[1] MsBackendMgf_1.16.0	SummarizedExperiment_1.38.1
[3] Biobase_2.68.0	GenomicRanges_1.60.0
[5] GenomeInfoDb_1.44.0	IRanges_2.42.0
[7] MatrixGenerics_1.20.0	matrixStats_1.5.0
[9] MetaboCoreUtils_1.17.1	pheatmap_1.0.12
[11] RColorBrewer_1.1-3	Spectra_1.18.2
[13] S4Vectors_0.46.0	BiocGenerics_0.54.0
[15] generics_0.1.4	MsExperiment_1.10.0
[17] ProtGenerics_1.40.0	xcms_4.6.0
[19] BiocParallel_1.42.1	BiocStyle_2.36.0
[21] knitr_1.50	

loaded via a namespace (and not attached):

[1] DBI_1.2.3	rlang_1.1.6
[3] magrittr_2.0.3	clue_0.3-66
[5] MassSpecWavelet_1.74.0	compiler_4.5.0
[7] vctrs_0.6.5	reshape2_1.4.4
[9] stringr_1.5.1	pkgconfig_2.0.3
[11] crayon_1.5.3	fastmap_1.2.0
[13] XVector_0.48.0	rmarkdown_2.29
[15] UCSC.utils_1.4.0	preprocessCore_1.70.0

[17]	purrr_1.0.4	xfun_0.52
[19]	MultiAssayExperiment_1.34.0	jsonlite_2.0.0
[21]	progress_1.2.3	DelayedArray_0.34.1
[23]	prettyunits_1.2.0	parallel_4.5.0
[25]	cluster_2.1.8.1	R6_2.6.1
[27]	stringi_1.8.7	limma_3.64.1
[29]	Rcpp_1.0.14	iterators_1.0.14
[31]	snow_0.4-4	BiocBaseUtils_1.10.0
[33]	Matrix_1.7-3	igraph_2.1.4
[35]	tidyselect_1.2.1	rstudioapi_0.17.1
[37]	abind_1.4-8	yaml_2.3.10
[39]	doParallel_1.0.17	codetools_0.2-20
[41]	affy_1.86.0	lattice_0.22-7
[43]	tibble_3.2.1	plyr_1.8.9
[45]	evaluate_1.0.3	pillar_1.10.2
[47]	affyio_1.78.0	BiocManager_1.30.25
[49]	foreach_1.5.2	MSnbase_2.34.1
[51]	MALDIquant_1.22.3	ncdf4_1.24
[53]	hms_1.1.3	ggplot2_3.5.2
[55]	scales_1.4.0	glue_1.8.0
[57]	MsFeatures_1.16.0	lazyeval_0.2.2
[59]	tools_4.5.0	mzID_1.46.0
[61]	QFeatures_1.18.0	vsn_3.76.0
[63]	mzR_2.42.0	fs_1.6.6
[65]	XML_3.99-0.18	grid_4.5.0
[67]	impute_1.82.0	tidyr_1.3.1
[69]	MsCoreUtils_1.20.0	colorspace_2.1-1
[71]	GenomeInfoDbData_1.2.14	PSMatch_1.12.0
[73]	cli_3.6.5	S4Arrays_1.8.1
[75]	dplyr_1.1.4	AnnotationFilter_1.32.0
[77]	pcaMethods_2.0.0	gtable_0.3.6
[79]	digest_0.6.37	SparseArray_1.8.0
[81]	htmlwidgets_1.6.4	farver_2.1.2
[83]	htmltools_0.5.8.1	lifecycle_1.0.4
[85]	httr_1.4.7	statmod_1.5.0
[87]	MASS_7.3-65	

4. Notes

1. Writing workflow processes using Quarto documents (.qmd) supports literate programming (**18**) by integrating code, text, and outputs in a single file. Quarto enables the creation of fully reproducible documents by embedding R code directly within narrative text, ensuring that results are dynamically generated from the most up-to-date data. This approach facilitates transparent, data-specific analysis workflows that are easy to audit, share, and update. By combining documentation and computation, Quarto helps streamline reporting, improve collaboration, and enhance the reproducibility of scientific and statistical analyses.
2. The workflow starts from vendor-neutral raw MS files, already converted from vendor-specific proprietary raw file formats (e.g., Thermo Fisher, Agilent, Bruker, Waters) to the open standard for MS data, i.e., the mzML format. Conversion of vendor-specific raw MS files is performed using *MSConvert*, a powerful and flexible tool from *ProteoWizard*. Using mzML as a standard format ensures that your MS data can be analyzed in a reproducible, tool-independent way.
3. R packages can be installed from the Comprehensive R Archive Network (CRAN) or from Bioconductor using the following commands:

```
#' Install CRAN packages
install.packages("knitr")

#' Install Bioconductor packages
install.packages("BiocManager")
BiocManager::install("BiocStyle")
```

4. The user can also read Excel (.xlsx) files using the `read_xlsx()` function from the `readxl` R package. However, the resulting object should be converted into a `data.frame` using `as.data.frame()` before beginning the analysis. Alternatively, the same tabular data can be created directly in R as a `data.frame`, but it is usually more practical and user-friendly to define and load the spreadsheet using a spreadsheet program.
5. For improved visualization, it is recommended to assign specific colors to individual samples as well as to sample groups. These color settings can be re-used in all plots during the analysis. Suggested color-coding schemes include: acquisition batch, injection order, sample type (e.g., QC, spiked, biological), and biological phenotypes of interest (e.g., sex, case-control status). These visual cues aid in assessing data quality and identifying potential systematic variation.
6. When no prior information is available about expected compounds, select high-intensity peaks from the BPC, extract full MS1 scans, and evaluate EICs to derive retention time and m/z parameters empirically.
7. Accurate peak detection, in particular with the *centWave* algorithm, requires centroided data. MS instruments allow to acquire data in profile or centroid mode. For profile mode all measured mass peaks in a spectrum are reported, while in centroid mode the data is reduced to a single representative mass peak for signal of one ion in a spectrum. If your data is not centroided, use `MSConvert` or a similar tool to convert profile mode data to centroid mode before importing it into R.
8. The m/z mass deviation is expressed as ppm and not in m/z difference (in Da) because the variation scales with the molecular mass of the compound. It is

important to estimate the ppm also on large compounds, as the ppm increases with larger compounds. For example, if your highest m/z detected is 1000 Da, and you have an estimated error of 5 ppm, the largest possible m/z deviation allowed is 1000 ± 0.005 Da (m/z mass deviation = $1000 \text{ Da} * 5 \text{ ppm} / 10^6$), ranging from 999.995 to 1000.005 Da.

9. The SummarizedExperiment container is a robust Bioconductor class that holds both assay data (e.g., intensity values) and associated metadata (e.g., feature and sample annotations in its `rowData()` and `colData()`, respectively). It provides a standardized format for integrating omics data and simplifies downstream manipulation or analysis.
10. Including a call to `sessionInfo()` at the end of the workflow is important for ensuring reproducibility, as it documents the versions of R and all loaded packages, as well as system-specific details that may influence results.

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